

FACTORS AFFECTING JOB SATISFACTION

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ABSTRACT

The task of educational institutions is to carry out a quality teaching and learning process, and the key is in the teacher. Therefore, the institution should ensure the quality of teacher performance is maintained. This study aims to identify several factors that affect teacher performance, but the measure is job satisfaction. This is intended to find out how the treatment of a teacher to carry out the task as well as possible, which is influenced by mood. To test the validity of the research, quantitative methods and structural equation modeling analysis were used. As for data collection techniques, researchers used a questionnaire, which was given directly to the respondent (teacher). The results showed, 1) Motivation to be a good mediator in influencing job satisfaction. 2) A good work culture can influence work behavior and shape work morale. 3) Low stress levels can affect teacher behavior to work better, because they are in a good mood (satisfied). This means that there are many non-physical factors that significantly affect teacher performance, including work culture, stress, and motivation. Therefore, in the aspect of human resource management, the treatment of institutions should be based on a humanitarian approach..

Keywords: Organization Culture, Stress, Motivation, Satisfaction

PROEM

The speed of change in all areas of life, as a result of globalization and the development of information technology, demands awareness of the importance of the quality of Human Resources (HR) which is one of the responses in response to these changes. Quality Human Resources (HR) is very important for the development of a nation. Even the availability of quality human resources is believed to be the main key to successful development, in order to create quality human beings, the world of education is required to play an active role in improving the quality of smart and independent human resources.

Education is very important in human resource development. Through education, humans can escape from backwardness. Education is also able to instill new capacities for humans to learn new knowledge and skills, so that productive and competitive humans can be obtained. It is quite a tough task for educational institutions both based on Islamic and general religions to be able to create competent, active, creative, and innovative human resources that lead to progress.

In improving the quality of good human resources, especially in educational institutions, especially teachers, there are many factors that must be considered in order to realize the quality of teachers in accordance with the progress of the times. One of the concerns of researchers is teacher satisfaction in carrying out their duties, if in teaching or educating students a teacher is satisfied with his work, it is hoped that it can have a big effect on the students being taught so that the educational goals are realized.

Teacher is a profession like any other profession which refers to a job or position that demands expertise, responsibility, and loyalty. Thus, creating professional teachers who can be good role models for students.

One of the efforts that can be made to improve teacher professionalism or performance is to build a sense of satisfaction. Considering that job satisfaction is a very important factor to get optimal work, when a person feels satisfaction at work, he will try as much as possible to the best of his ability, to complete his job duties.

Robbins (2015) explains that job satisfaction is a general attitude towards one's job, the difference between the amount of reward a worker receives and the amount they believe they should receive. Satisfaction occurs when individual needs have been met, and is related to the degree of liking or dislike, associated with employees. As for the general attitude that employees have that is closely related to the rewards they believe they will receive after making a sacrifice. From the explanation, it is clear that explicitly the satisfaction of a teacher can be achieved if everything related to their needs can be fulfilled in accordance with their respective characteristics. In addition, job satisfaction also demands more treatment. This means that institutional treatment can make a teacher feel appreciated and given encouragement to be able to work. For example, given promotions or structural positions.

Further research by Boamah, et al. (2018) proves that job satisfaction can give birth to unexpected levels of work, employees will show a loyal and caring attitude

towards the agency, even employees feel proud to have been able to work for the agency. This explanation seems clear that a sense of satisfaction can lead to positive work behavior, full of enthusiasm, good results-oriented, totality in work, nimble and so on (De Simone, et al., 2018; Chadi & Hetschko, 2018).

In line with the previous discussion, one of the efforts that can be made to generate teacher satisfaction is motivation. According to Zainal, et al. (2019). Motivation is a series of attitudes and values that influence individuals to achieve specific things in accordance with individual goals. These attitudes and values are *invisible* which provide strength to encourage behavior in achieving goals. This theory explains that motivation is an impulse that is born inside and outside to do a job with all its capabilities, in order to achieve the desired goals. In other words, motivation is the main asset in doing a job, especially teaching. Teachers are required to have an extra role, meaning that they are not only able to explain subjects, but they must be able to comprehensively master the class, have good teaching methods and become role models for students.

These reasons ultimately require teachers to be more motivated in educating students with high patience, diligence, and good emotional intelligence. Therefore, motivation in the individual teacher is needed in educating and fostering students as expected.

As the results of research conducted by Ayalew, et al. (2019), the results of this study prove that work motivation partially and simultaneously has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. In fact, the results of his research show that the motivation factor is one of the most dominant in increasing job satisfaction, which in turn has an impact on increasing employee performance (Nur, et al., 2019; Rahman, et al., 2019).

Another factor that also influences is organizational culture. According to Chung & Ahn (2019) organizational culture is ways of thinking, feeling, and reacting based on certain patterns that exist within the organization or that exist in parts of the organization. Is a mental programming of the organization, which is a reflection of the 'model' of organizational personality. Organizational personality 'capital' is the degree of homogeneity and strength of a specific personality orientation within an organization.

This theory means that organizational culture is a provision of values, norms, and ethics made by an institution or organization to be obeyed by its members to achieve predetermined goals. In other words, there is an agreement that occurs scientifically / consciously carried out by members in supporting good performance.

This provides an explanation that culture is a set of attitudes and work behaviors that reflect special characteristics, which distinguish one organization from another. In fact, it is not uncommon for organizational culture to be an effective tool in building harmonious working relationships.

In most cases even organizational culture can create a conducive work environment, when compared to compensation, so that there are some employees who for that reason feel comfortable, and feel at home working.

As the results of research conducted by Fikry, et al. (2020), the results of this study prove that organizational culture partially and simultaneously has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. The results of his research indicate that organizational culture is one of the factors that can increase teacher job satisfaction, so that it has an impact on increasing teacher performance (Meng & Berger, 2019).

Apart from the variables of motivation and organizational culture that can generate and increase teacher job satisfaction, another factor is job stress. Work stress according to Kivimäki & Kawachi (2015) is stress is a condition of tension that affects one's emotions, thought processes and condition. Too much stress can threaten a person's ability to deal with the environment. From the theoretical explanation, job stress is an inhibiting factor for teacher job satisfaction, which in turn has an impact on teacher performance. This gives a sign that work stress is not an ordinary problem, considering that work stress often occurs in the world of education, considering that teaching work is quite draining and mindful.

THEORETIC

Teacher job satisfaction is an important point in determining and achieving the goals of an educational institution, but before we discuss teacher job satisfaction, we will discuss the embryo of teacher job satisfaction, namely the attitude of a person in expressing his feelings in evaluating his work.

According to Robbins (2015) "Viewing job satisfaction as the overall result of the degree of likes or dislikes workers towards various aspects of their work. In other words, job satisfaction reflects the attitude of workers towards their work.

While the simple limit that can be taken is that the higher the job satisfaction, the better a person's performance in carrying out his duties. And in this case the study will examine teacher performance as the affected variable. The definition of a teacher according to Irawati, et al (2019) is "A person who has the ability and experience that can facilitate in carrying out his role in guiding his students, he must be able to assess himself without exaggeration, be able to communicate and cooperate with others.

Thus we know that teachers are not only in charge of teaching but must also have experience in educating their students, guiding and directing their students to become human beings with noble character and high intellect, therefore this profession requires special expertise in the field of education.

Motivation is an aspect that is no less important in the world of work, which raises many questions from leaders why there are employees who work hard but some are lazy. This problem also occurs among teachers, where there are teachers who work quite hard in teaching their knowledge but there are also teachers who often skip classes and easily let go of their responsibilities. In the case that happens there are some teachers who are willing to sacrifice their time and energy just to teach their knowledge in remote areas of the village even though sometimes they are not paid, it must have crossed our minds, what motivation can make a teacher do all of that voluntarily.

As stated by Robbins in defining motivation is "a process that explains knowing the strength, direction and persistence of a person in an effort to achieve goals" in this sense it has been explained that a person can do something harder because he has a goal and is more focused if someone clearly knows definitely the purpose of the organization, in an effort to achieve this goal emerges strength (*intensity*) which describes how hard a person tries. This is the element that takes center stage when we talk about motivation. However, this power must be channeled in *adirection* that benefits the institution. Therefore, we must consider direction and strength in order to be in tune and balance and consistent with the goals of the institution and the last one is that motivation efforts must have *persistence*. Persistence measures how long a person can

maintain his efforts. People who are motivated will stick with the task long enough to achieve their goals.

Chung & Ahn (2019) suggest that organizational culture affects the behavior of members or individuals and groups in an organization, in this case this behavior also affects the achievement of these achievements and simultaneously affects the effectiveness or failure of achievement. organization goals. Therefore, in brief it can be said that organizational culture is very influential on organizational effectiveness. The values in school greatly affect the motivation of teachers at work. In order to know what to do and what not to do, it requires rules and values that can be applied and agreed upon by the organization, so that it becomes clear about the rules and behavior of the teachers towards others or interacting with the santri or santri guardians.

Job stress is a factor inhibiting a person in carrying out their duties properly, a person who experiences symptoms of stress or pressure at work will tend to cause psychological, physical and behavioral weakness in adapting to their environment. Stress is something that is concerned with the interaction between people and the environment as a stimulant interaction (stimulus), response interaction (response) or interactions between stimulants and responses (stimulus-response interaction).

METHOD

The scope of this research is human resource management, which specifically examines the behavior of employees, and in this study several scientific efforts are needed, including:

1. Using quantitative methods. The reason is that this approach has the convenience of testing and analyzing data.
2. Using a structural equation model analysis. The Model which provides a structured overview, making it easier for research in generating the recommendation.
3. Using a questionnaire as a research instrument
4. The sampling technique used simple random technique was
5. The research population was teachers
6. The unit of analysis was 120 people
7. The data collection carried out directly by providing a questionnaire

RESULT

Variable Measurement

1. The elements of work satisfaction include the type of work, colleagues, benefits, treated with respect and fairness, job security, opportunities to contribute ideas, wages, recognition of performance and opportunities for advancement. All indicators have good validity values and can explain variables, but the most dominant indicator is allowances. This means that the teachers will feel happier if they get more compensation. This psychologically explains, receiving financial kindness can stimulate feelings of pleasure. In a broad sense, happiness is in line with the necessities of life (Anjilus, et al., 2019; Bakar & Alias, 2020).
2. The Dimensions of motivation are (1) physiological needs. (2) taste needs safe. (3) social needs. (4) need for appreciation. (5) self-actualization needs. The interesting thing from the research results is that social needs are the biggest motivation for a teacher. That is, teachers become happier (satisfied) if they get a social life while carrying out their assignments. These findings confirm the theory, that satisfaction is close to hospitality, and it is derived from social interactions (Irawati, et al., 2019). The research conducted by Nur, et al. (2019) explained that actually work life is a new form of social life, people interact with each other in terms of work, and what attracts everyone to work together to achieve happiness (goals).
3. The measured organizational culture is: (1) organizational values, (2) management support, (3) reward system, (4)) Tolerance in sharing mistakes as an opportunity to learn, (5) Orientation to the details (details) of work, (6) Orientation to the team. Cooperation indicators are the main parameter in explaining organizational culture variables . This means, in fact, the work culture that is currently being built is due to the cooperation between teachers, mutually reinforcing one another, and because of that the work culture continues (Batugal & Tindowen, 2019). As research has suggested, habits require strength, and the greatest support comes from an environment that both do.
4. Operational work stress variables are measured using 3 (three) indicators adopted from Robbins' opinion about work stress symptoms, namely : (1) Physiological Symptoms, (2) Psychological Symptoms, and Behavioral Symptoms. The research findings show that the stress behavior that appears is psychological. This means

that when a teacher experiences stress, what appears is selfish attitudes, such as irritability, irritability, anxiety, and excessive fear (Parveen & Bano, 2019; Kamneva, Eet al., 2019). This is in line with the statement of a research, stress is synonymous with mental disorders, so direct disturbance from someone who experiences it is a bad attitude, if it continues, it will show bad behavior (Karabatak & Alanoglu, 2019).

Result

The results showed a good model, either directly or indirectly, organizational culture has a significant effect on job satisfaction. The interesting thing is that work culture will contribute better if it is through work motivation. This means that teachers will work better, if they are satisfied, and satisfaction will be born if there is motivation, and enthusiasm will emerge when the work culture becomes the basis for carrying out their duties. These findings theoretically reinforce the fact that the relationship between satisfaction and motivation is very strong, and both will have a very large impact on performance. Of course, all of these series will only be achieved if the organization can build a good work culture. A culture that is oriented towards strengthening attitudes and behavior, a culture that builds good character, a culture that creates a positive work environment, and a culture that encourages the birth of professional work. In the research proposed by Batugal & Tindowen (2019), organizational culture is an identity that allows every teacher to realize that their role is a carrier of change, so any behavior that emerges must contribute to change and progress.

Statistically, the work stress variable shows good results. The model obtained is significant negative. This means that increased stress can reduce motivation and job satisfaction, and this will have a negative impact on teacher performance, especially for institutions. Conversely, if job stress decreases, morale and satisfaction will increase. These findings confirm that scientifically job stress is a confounding factor that can significantly affect morale, job satisfaction, and performance. Explicitly, this situation will have a bad impact and disrupt the progress of the institution, which in turn threatens its existence. Research conducted by Parveen & Bano (2019) explains that job stress is a qualitative factor that is privacy in nature, but the impact is very bad for both individual employees and the organization itself.

CONCLUSION

Based on statistical calculations, we get pretty good results. Where, organizational culture becomes the independent variable that has a dominant direct effect on job satisfaction. This means that in the teacher's workspace, work culture is a factor that affects the attitudes and behavior of teachers at work. Such as an attitude of integrity, an attitude that upholds the values of kindness and ethics, so that in every implementation of the duties of the teachers always behave honestly.

The work stress variable shows a good relationship statistically. Where the relationship model is reversed. That is, if the stress factor is getting smaller, then job satisfaction increases and has an impact on performance.

The role of motivation in the structural model is full mediation. This means that good work behavior will be maintained if the teachers have high satisfaction, and this satisfaction is influenced by work motivation, where work morale itself is influenced by a strong culture and at least work stress disorders.

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